

D6.3

First report on training courses/workshops

Daniele Varsano, Ivan Giroto, Ivan Marri, Luisa Neri,
and Stefan Blügel

Due date of deliverable:	28/02/2017
Actual submission date:	28/02/2017
Final version:	28/02/2017
Revised version:	dd/mm/201y
Revised version submission:	dd/mm/201y

Lead beneficiary:	Jülich (participant number 4)
Consortium members contributing:	CNR SISS ICN2 JUEL EPFL CIN BSC ETHZ KTH CW ICTP
Dissemination level:	PU - Public

Document information

Project acronym:	MaX
Project full title:	Materials Design at the Exascale
Research Action Project type:	European Centre of Excellence in materials modelling, simulations and design
EC Grant agreement no.:	676598
Project starting / end date:	01/09/2015 (month 1) / 28/02/2018 (month 30)
Website:	www.max-centre.eu
Deliverable No.:	D6.3

Authors: Daniele Varsano, Ivan Girotto, Ivan Marri, Luisa Neri, and Stefan Blügel

To be cited as: D. Varsano, I. Girotto, I. Marri, L. Neri, and S. Blügel (2017): First report on training courses/workshops. Deliverable D6.3 of the H2020 project MaX (final version as of 28/12/2017). EC grant agreement no: 676598, Jülich, Germany.

Disclaimer:

This document's contents are not intended to replace consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

D6.3 First report on training courses/workshops

Content

1	Executive Summary	4
2	Repository of existing initiatives	4
3	Training events	5
3.1	Courses on individual codes/ HPC developments/on new methods-software developments/ applications & extensions for industry	5
3.2	Participation of MaX members as teachers in other schools	12
3.3	University courses modules.	12
3.4	Training through research	13
4.	Conclusion	14
5.	Attachments	14

1 Executive Summary

Deliverable 6.3 reports on the education and training activities, including data on users participation and involvement. In D6.1 we had proposed our structured Education and Training plan, aimed at bridging the skills gap between HPC development and computational materials science. This plan is being effectively implemented through different actions, which in the first 18 months include:

- a. Eight training initiatives --schools, tutorials, workshops-- directly designed, organized and co-funded by MaX (sometimes in cooperation with others). The emphasis was on hands-on-activities based on MaX flagship codes and frontier HPC developments, and on the involvement of young participants. The overall assessment of these initiatives by the participants (approx 400 in total) was extremely positive.
- b. A few lectures / modules offered by MaX within schools organized by other institutions.
- c. Major contributions to innovative education pilots within three University MSci courses, plus one MOOC course under development.

These initiatives have resulted in the production of valuable training material, that have been handed out to students in preliminary form and will be made available to the broader community in the next months, once refined.

Most partners have been heavily involved in the activities: Juelich, CNR, SISSA, ICN2, EPFL, CINECA, BSC, ETH Zürich, KTH, CloudWeavers, and UNESCO. Importantly, a significant number of activities have combined synergic contributions from different MaX partners with complementary expertise.

Finally, MaX is maintaining an on-line repository of training initiatives of interest to the computational materials research community, which is useful to potential participants and also helps organizers in coordinating, identifying needs and avoiding overlaps.

2 Repository of existing initiatives

MaX maintains a repository with information on training courses and workshop of relevance for its domain and community. This is available in the MaX website (see D6.2 for details) at the address <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/>. A list of events is given at the page <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/list-of-workshops-schools/> where events organized or supported directly by MaX are conveniently flagged.

More information on the activities organized or supported by MaX are also displayed at the Events section of the website.

3 Training events

3.1 Courses on individual codes/ HPC developments/on new methods-software developments/ applications & extensions for industry

As defined in D6.1 chapter 3, MaX is engaged to organize specific training workshops and courses dedicated to scientists in the materials field, at different levels, with emphasis on hands-on courses. The aim is to give training by providing technical information and knowledge attracting especially young researchers. This task is coordinated by SISSA and CNR.

In the following a description of schools and training workshops organized by MaX until month 18. According to MaX strategy, we have chosen to organize directly a limited number of events of direct relevance for the CoE activities (other training actions are described in the following sections). Note that these seven events have often involved the contribution of more than one (sometimes several) partners of MaX.

List of school:

1. AiiDA tutorial and coding days
2. Python for computational science
3. Linear response workshop 2016
4. Tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA
5. Introductory School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for High-Performance Computing
6. TBtrans AND TranSiesta Tutorial: Non-Equilibrium Green Functions from Tight Binding to Self-Consistency
7. Materials Science codes on Innovative HPC architectures: targeting Exascale
8. Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using QUANTUM ESPRESSO

1. AiiDA tutorial and coding days.

Venue & date: EPFL, Lausanne (CH). 02-03/11/2015.

Organizers: MaX, Marvel.

Speakers: Nicola Marzari, Giovanni Pizzi, Spyros Zoupanos, Nicola Mounet, Andrea Cepellotti, Martin Uhrin, Snehal Waychal

Topics: Users' tutorial: Introduction to the code, job submission, data retrieval, setup of new computers & codes and query of results. Developers' tutorial: Example of plugins' development in AiiDA and details on the platform internals. From November 4 to 6: "Coding days" for people interested in the development of new plugins for AiiDA.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 40

Involvement: The feedback on the school is given in attachment (see D6.3-A1 below). The overall level of satisfaction is definitely very positive.

Website: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/en/events/aiida-tutorial-coding-days>

2. Python for computational science.

Venue & date: University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Modena (IT). 25-27/01/2016.

Organizers: MaX, Cineca.

Speakers: N. Spallanzani and M. Cestari

Topics: Introduction to the python 3 programming language. Python syntax: philosophy, interpreter, built-in types and operations, program file, built-in containers, flow control constructs, object reference, functions, sequences, output representation, classes, iterables and iterators, introspection, modules, file I/O, error handling.

Fortran to python interface generator F2PY.

Ipython and matplotlib, object oriented interface.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 26

Involvement: The course received very positive feedback from the participants. For details see attachment D6.3-A2 below.

Website: <http://www.hpc.cineca.it/content/python-computational-science-0>

3. Linear response workshop 2016.

Venue & date: Sissa, Trieste (IT). 18-21/01/2016.

Organizers: MaX, Quantum Espresso Foundation.

Speakers: F. Affinito, S. Baroni, M. Buongiorno Nardelli, M. Cococcioni, N. Colonna, A. Dal Corso, A. Floris, S. de Gironcoli, X. Ge, U. Gerstmann, P. Giannozzi, T. Gorni, M. Govoni, H. Lambert, L. Paulatto, S. Poncé, D. Rocca, I. Timrov, P. Umari, N. Varini, N. Vast.

Topics: General introduction to the Quantum ESPRESSO project and to linear response, including current state of parallelisation and optimisation.

PHonon with USPP/PAW and spin-orbit interactions.

Symmetry in Phonon. Phonon-phonon interaction and the D3 code.

TDDFT: absorption spectroscopy for finite systems, applications to crystals (EELS).

GW & BSE. ACFDT & van der-Waals interaction.

Electron-phonon interaction. GIPAW – linear response in the presence of magnetic fields.

Intel KNL and new challenges for material science codes. DFPT + U.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 28

Involvement: The goal of the workshop was bring together developers of different codes, working on linear response, and to work together on a modularization, restructuring, and unification of various linear-response codes. Developers of the flagship codes QE and Yambo actively participated in this meeting.

Website: <http://www.quantum-espresso.org/resources/advanced-quantum-espresso-developers-meeting-linear-response/>

4. Tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using AiiDA.

Venue & date: EPFL, Lausanne (CH). 22-24/06//2016.

Organizers: MaX, Marvel, Psi-K.

Speakers: A. Cepellotti, F. Gargiulo, G. Pizzi, L. Kahle, M. Uhrin, N. Mounet, S. Waychal, S. Zoupanos (EPFL, CH). G. Csányi (Uni Cambridge, UK). G. Hautier (Uni Catholique de Louvain, BE). K. S. Thygesen (DTU, DK).

Topics: Hands-on tutorial: browsing in the AiiDA graph, getting inputs and outputs.

Computational screening for new solar energy materials. Submitting calculations. Querying the database. Installation, guidelines for writing, provenance and workflows in AiiDA.

An AiiDA use case: 2D materials, plugins.

Fitting interatomic potentials to moderate and large amounts of DFT data.

Accelerating materials discovery through high-throughput computing and data mining.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 57

Involvement: The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive. A detailed report of the event is found in the attachment D6.3-A3 below.

Website: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/en/events/aiida-tutorial-june-2016>.

Report on the event: <http://psi-k.net/aiida-tutorial-report-june-2016/>

5. Introductory School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for High-Performance Computing.

Venue & date: ICTP, Trieste (IT). 03-14/10/2016.

Organizers: MaX, EPCC, PSC.

Speakers: M. O. Atambo (UniMORE, IT); S. Bna' (CINECA, IT); S. Brown (Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center, US); N. Cavallini (MHPC SISSA, IT); S. De Gironcoli (SISSA & DEMOCRITOS, IT); I. Girotto (ICTP, IT); G. Giuliani (ICTP, IT); L. Heltai (SISSA, IT); G. Pringle (EPCC, University of Edinburgh, UK) S. F. Schifano (Unife, IT)

Topics: Introduction to HPC. Foundation of Modern Computer Architectures for HPC. Measuring Hardware Performance. Floating point. From Source Code to Executable. Mixing C++, C, Fortran. Manual Code Optimization and via Compiler Options.

Lab-Session: Multi-Language Programming. Simple Examples of Code Optimization.

Basic Principles of Parallelism. OpenMP. Practical MPI.

Overview of Common Strategies for Parallelization. Overview of Parallel Profiling: Why and How. Parallel Approaches To Lattice Boltzman Method. Parallelising Wave Front Simulations. HPC for DFT. Foundations of Parallel I/O. Foundation of HDF5.

deal.II: A Numerical Library to Tackle Realistic Challenges from Industry and Academia. Parallel FFTs and the FFTW library. Sparse Matrix Computations with PETSc. Solving large

Eigenvalue problems with Trilinos. Overview of Mesh Decomposition.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes. Course on HPC development.

No. participants: 45

Involvement: not available

Website: <http://indico.ictp.it/event/7659/overview>

6. TBtrans AND TranSiesta Tutorial: Non-Equilibrium Green Functions from Tight Binding to Self-Consistency.

Venue & date: ICN2 Building, UAB, Barcelona (ES). 9-11/11/2016.

Organizers: MaX, NFFA.

Speakers: A. Cepellotti, F. Gargiulo, G. Pizzi, L. Kahle, M. Uhrin, N. Mounet, S. Waychal, S. Zoupanos (EPFL, CH). G. Csányi (Uni Cambridge, UK). G. Hautier (Uni Catholique de Louvain, BE). K. S. Thygesen (DTU, DK).

Topics: Theory: Non-equilibrium Green function theory. Introduction to TranSiesta. NEGF for N-electrode calculations.

Tutorial: Tight-binding and TBtrans. Data analysis for TBtrans. Advanced tight-binding for TBtrans (N-electrode). TranSiesta calculations (also for N-electrodes).

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 25

Involvement: not available

Website: <http://icn2.cat/en/events/eventdetail/223/open-knowledge-program-module-7-tbtrans-and-transiesta-tutorial-non-equilibrium-green-functions-from-tight-binding-to-self-consistency>

7. Materials Science codes on Innovative HPC architectures: targeting Exascale.

Venue & date: Cineca, Bologna (IT). 5-7/12/2016.

Organizers: MaX, Prace.

Speakers: C. Cavazzoni, F. Affinito, M. Ippolito, N. Spallanzani (CINECA, IT). A. Kozhenikov (CSCS, CH). D. Sangalli (CNR, IT). O. Dieguez (TAU, IL). D. Wortmann (Jülich, DE).

Topics: Introduction to MaX infrastructures (Cineca Tier 0 Marconi, CSCS infrastructure). Introduction to some of the main code used by the material science community: QE, Siesta, Yambo, qe-lammps, FLEUR.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses covering all the MaX flagship codes.

No. participants: 18

Involvement: The school was rated as very good by the majority of students. For details see attachment D6.3-A4 below.

Website: <https://events.prace-ri.eu/event/559/>

Mariella Ippolito, Cineca Lecture about QM/MM

8. Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using QUANTUM ESPRESSO.

Venue & date: ICTP, Trieste (IT). 16/1/2017.

Organizers: MaX, Quantum Espresso Foundation, CECAM, ECAM, MARVEL, Psi-K.

Speakers: S. Baroni (SISSA & Democritos, IT). R. Innocente, A. Dal Corso, L. Isaeva, I. Timrov, M. Palumbo (SISSA, IT). P. Giannozzi (Univ. Udine, IT). A. Marini (ISM-CNR, IT). D. Ceresoli (CNR-ISTM, IT). M. Cococcioni, N. Colonna, O. Andreussi (EPFL, CH). G. Pizzi, F. Gargiulo, S. Huber, L. Kahle, S. Waychal (THEOS and MARVEL, EPFL, Lausanne). S. Scandolo, R. Gebauer (ICTP, IT). L. Paulatto (IMPIC, FR). A. Ferretti (CNR NANO, IT). M. Ceriotti, R. Petraglia (EPFL STI IMX COSMO, CH). C. Cavazzoni (CINECA, IT).

Topics: DFT fundamentals: from theory to practice. Basics of ab-initio Molecular Dynamics. Linear Response, density-functional perturbation theory. Phonon calculations and thermodynamic. Vibrational & Magnetic Spectroscopies in QE. GW and MBPT calculations using QE and Yambo. Introduction to AiiDA, the ADES model and the concept of provenance. Advanced Molecular Dynamics. Evolution of Present and Future HPC Architectures.

Type of event (see T6.1): Courses on individual codes.

No. participants: 65 selected attendees (selected from over 270 received applications)

Involvement: The overall rate for this school is very good. See detailed report at attachment D6.3-A5 below.

Website: <http://indico.ictp.it/event/7921/>

3.2 Participation of MaX members as teachers in other schools

The activity of MaX members in training goes far beyond the organization of schools and workshops. Some lectures about codes, HPC, and modeling were offered within training events organized by others (sometimes such training activity can overlap with dissemination, when the events are also directed to peers). We consider this contribution very valuable also in view of its impact on networking.

A list of lectures offered by MaX members is given below.

1. 14/7/2016. Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL, CH).
AiiDA tutorial for users.
 In College on Multiscale Computational Modeling of Materials for Energy Applications. ICTP, Trieste (IT).
 Website: <http://indico.ictp.it/event/7656/overview>
2. 13/06/2016. Michele Ceriotti (EPFL, CH).
Accelerating Path Integral Calculations.
 In Path Integral Quantum Mechanics: Theory, Simulation and Application. CECAM EPFL, Lausanne (CH).
 Website: <https://www.cecam.org/workshop-1314.html>
3. 1-11/02/2016. Stefano Baroni (Sissa, IT).
Density-functional perturbation theory: response functions, phonons, and all that.
Density-functional perturbation theory goes time-dependent.
 In EUSpec Winter School on Core Level Spectroscopies, University of Nova Gorica, Ajdovščina (SI).
 Website: <http://www.euspec.eu/dates/66-winter-school-on-core-level-spectroscopies>
5. 28/9-2/10/2015. Stefano Baroni (Sissa, IT).
Density-functional perturbation theory: response functions, phonons, and all that.
Density-functional perturbation theory goes time-dependent.
Computer simulation of thermally activated processes with QUANTUM ESPRESSO
 In QUANTUM ESPRESSO Spring School, Córdoba (AR).
 Website: <http://www.euspec.eu/dates/66-winter-school-on-core-level-spectroscopies>
4. 14/9/2015. Andrea Ferretti (Cnr Nano, IT).
Ab initio modelling in solid state chemistry in Crystal Developers.
 In: 2015 MSSC Summer School on the "ab initio modelling of crystalline and defective solids with the CRYSTAL code". London Imperial College (UK).
 Website: <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/mssc2015>

3.3 University courses modules.

In the MaX's training plan special attention was paid to Master/PhD students and University teachers, who wish to learn the use of frontier computational methods within their domain. In order to do so, several commitments were taken and have been realized (or started to realize).

1. MaX (ICTP and SISSA teams) contributed to the joint SISSA/ICTP Master in High-Performance Computing (MHPC) (<http://mhpc.it>) with a set of dedicated lectures on frontiers developments:

- QE, main strategies of parallelization and levels of parallelisms/ QE and many-core architectures, F. Affinito (Cineca, IT). 2016.
 - Introduction to Computer Architecture for HPC, I. Girotto (ICTP, IT). 2016.
 - Parallel Programming, I. Girotto (ICTP, IT). 2016.
 - Parallel FFT, I. Girotto & R. Gebauer (ICTP, IT). 2017.
 - Monte Carlo Methods, S. Baroni (SISSA, IT). 2017.
 - Levels & Hierarchy of Parallelism in Quantum ESPRESSO, S. De Gironcoli (SISSA, IT). 2017.
2. MaX (Cnr team) contributed to the MSci Course in Physics of the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, IT, by participating in the design and realization of a new course entitled “Laboratory of Computational Quantum Mechanics”, particularly for what concerns the ‘hands-on’ activities that were performed on MaX flagship codes. This initiative was developed by Andrea Ferretti and Daniele Varsano from MaX (Cnr Nano, IT), together with Professor Alice Ruini who is in charge of the course for the University. In addition to the planning, Drs Ferretti and Varsano have taken part in seven laboratory sessions; based on this experience, they are currently exploring the possibility of further developments. Number of students: 8. Website: <https://tinyurl.com/hdgt66w>
 3. A. pilot course (12 ECTS) titled “Electronic Structure: from blackboard to source code” was prepared by professor S. De Gironcoli at SISSA, given at Fudan Intensive Summer Training 2016 from 1 to 19 August 2016 and a reduced version will be offered in the MHPC in Trieste in May 2017. The course aims in providing the students with a detailed knowledge of the internal design of *state of the art* electronic structure codes, filling the gap that exists between the knowledge of the general principles underlying modern atomistic simulations and their practical implementation in actual codes. Tools and codes available in the *Open Source* Quantum ESPRESSO software distribution will be used as working examples. This activity has been done in synergy with the E-CAM CoE. The detailed syllabus is found in the attachment D6.3-A6 below. Slides of the course are available at MaX’s website on the “[open online courses and videolectures](#)” page.
 4. As planned, Massive Open Online Course are being developed by MaX in collaboration with ICTP and EPFL. Recording and editing for preparation of video lectures were done in the occasion of the “Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using QUANTUM ESPRESSO”, (January 16-28 2017) and will soon be available at the following link: <https://slideshot.epfl.ch/events/17>. The videos will be soon hosted in this EFL’s platform and will be linked to MaX website as well. Recording from MaX’s training events is also available for the “TBtrans and TranSiesta Tutorial: Non-Equilibrium Green Functions from Tight Binding to Self-Consistency” held in Barcelona. Videos will soon be publicly available at website <http://icn2.cat/en/open-knowledge-program>.

3.4 Training through research

“Training through research” in the CoE labs is being coordinated by ICN2 and CNR. We consider that this may become a powerful instrument both for industrial researchers and for academic researchers/PhD students. An excellent experience was done, across the early months of MaX, by the partner CNR that hosted two researchers (from Toyota and Total) for

training on new tribochemistry-oriented applications.

MaX is now ready and eager to offer internships of short/medium duration to experienced researchers and PhD students willing to gain experience with the MaX flagship codes. The training through research activities are explained in a specific page in the website: <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/training-through-research-in-the-coe-labs/>.

We have included ‘Training through research’ among the services offered through the Users Portal (see D5.2) and plan to further promote it in the next months.

4. Conclusion

The training plan outlined in D6.1 offered a roadmap to MaX partners in organizing their training activities. All groups already had a strong expertise in offering training to students and users, which has been boosted by the CoE’s willingness of crossing borders among codes. Participation and involvement show the overall success of the events.

We plan to organize again some of the courses and to add more tailored training to users: all new plans will be made with the on-going success of the MaX project in mind, allowing for educational resources and support to be available to the wider scientific community. In several cases we will repeat successful initiatives to respond to the existing demand, and will take advantage of the previous experience and cross-fertilization with other courses¹.

We are confident that the investment in producing training materials, and the experience gained through pilot initiatives, will be the key to better training with less effort already in the next months.

5. Attachments

- D6.3-A1 Feedback from the Aiida tutorial, November 2015
- D6.3-A2 Report on the “Python for Scientific Computing” tutorial.
- D6.3-A3 scientific report on the workshop: “marvel/max/psi-k tutorial on high-Throughput computations: general methods and applications using Aiida”
- D6.4-A4 Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale
- D6.4-A5 Scientific Report on the Workshop: "Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using Quantum ESPRESSO"
- D6.4-A6 “Electronic Structure: from blackboard to source code” syllabus

¹ For example, a second edition of the “Tutorial on high-throughput computations: general methods and applications using Aiida”, co-organized with MARVEL and Psi-k, will take place at EPFL in Lausanne at the end of May 2017.

Feedback from the AiiDA tutorial – November 2015

Everything works! However I was a bit annoyed by the windows machines, maybe it's possible to provide Unix machines next time?

I learned a lot by doing the exercises, but maybe some general introduction additionally to the exercise section presenting the functionality of AiiDa would be nice.

Add in the cookbook the possibility how to check the md5sum of an executable. Programmatically install a computer or a code.

Great training performed by talented and great people.

congratulation to the team!

A user tried to change the default plugin of the code by doing:

```
...  
code = Code.get_from_string(codename)  
code.set_input_plugin_name('floatsum')  
calc = code.new_calc()  
...
```

This changed the default plugin of the code. The name of the function "set_input_plugin_name" doesn't give the impression that the default plugin of the code will change.

To use an arbitrary input plugin (and not the default one) with a specific code, the user should do:

```
...  
calc = CalculationFactory('floatsum')  
calc.use_code(code)  
...
```

This should be documented and the first option should be avoided (write it clearly in the doc)

Add documentation on groups and how to use them

Add documentation on:

- how to create groups;
- how to add calculations to a group;
- how to delete a group.

I liked the hands-on approach mixed with little background info as one really learns stuff that way. Superb organization and very competent crew of instructors and also a great way to discuss with people trying to achieve similar things and to coordinate efforts.

For me as somewhat of a python novice it could have been good to have a list of the python constructs one would not typically know from C/C++ or fortran beforehand so I could have read up on them. Stuff like setters, decoration, etc. This could have made the coding part less painful and allowed me to focus more on AiiDA rather than fixing novice Python mistakes.

Nevertheless I feel like I learned my (basic) way around AiiDA, how to debug stuff and should be able to use it for what I want to.

Thanks for the great tutorial!

Even if for my research I would have preferred more details about the use of AiiDA for Quantum Espresso, I appreciated both days. The second day was maybe too advanced for my basic understanding of python but I could have a feeling of how your software works and so what are its potentials.

I think that the choice of leaving a lot of "freedom" during the tutorial was good because everyone could work at his own speed, having the opportunity to make questions in case of problems.

I would appreciate if I could receive the result scripts of the second day to verify my work.

Thank you.

The organization, place and resources were good and everything worked without problems apart from the vi editor in the local machine, which kept doing strange things when pasting or deleting data.

The general explanations were fine but probably a bit difficult for those without a prior knowledge of AiiDA, and of course without too much knowledge of python. Some explanations were also a bit quick and it was difficult to take notes. It would be good to have access to the transparencies after the tutorial.

About day 1:

The idea is really good, but I guess you'd have to have a reasonable python knowledge to make the most of the day (e.g. I spent quite some time just dealing with syntax errors - even if I got the basic concepts). Maybe state that in the announcement? So one can come prepared...

I think that an intermediate exercise between the first, easy one, and the 3rd, where you basically have to write your code from scratch would be useful. In alternative you could maybe improve the comments in the sample codes so that one knows which parts can be recycled for the third part.

The exercises of the tutorial were well written. Maybe it could be useful to have more support, at least in the first part of the tutorial. For example one of the developers could show in real time how to practically proceed to solve the exercises.

Really good! I learned a lot, well organized and very helpful!

The tutorial was very well organised and I found it useful.

My only small suggestions are:

- a) Stress a bit more on the requirement of knowing python (I'd have started learning it earlier)
 - b) At the really beginning I would do an "exercise 0" just running common enquiry on, for instance, a QE job. Then exercise 1 how to run that job etc.
- First of all thanks for the courtesy and the competence demonstrated. The user tutorial was fine. Probably the developer tutorial needs to be extended. For instance starting the tutorial with a short refresh of some not so basic features of python, like properties and decorators, just a refresh. Then would be useful also a little more detailed explanation of what AiiDA does when interact with a plugin.

Dear AiiDA team,

Thank you very much for a very intense and interesting tutorial. I'm very satisfied by what I've learned. As good points I would select the following:

- 1) People are friendly and always available to provide help when needed.
- 2) Working environment, quality of learning materials.
- 3) Hotel, social dinner.

What could be improved, in my opinion:

- 1) I think that second day was a bit too intense. For me workflows were already too much. I would prefer to focus more on creating of data objects and plugins. I would put workflows as a third day, or just briefly mention them at the end of the second one.
- 2) I would remove (if possible) json thing from the second day. It just makes non-important things a bit more complicated.

Dear AiiDA tutorial organizers,

first of all many thanks for the perfect organization of the AiiDA experience. The tutorial was very well thought, both the user and the plugin developer part. I have now a very clear idea of what AiiDA can do, and potentially do in the future. Moreover I'm very happy about the interest and help for the yambo plugin. Unfortunately I'm not a python native speaker (actually I got my first basic rudiments last week) so I had some difficulties in following all the details and I was very slow in the exercises. Anyway it was very useful to me. Many thanks again!!!

A very good workshop and a very useful discussion!

A few points, that I would personally change:

- 1) Start from the basics of installation of AiiDA to a personal laptop (I spent ~1 day on that topic because I was doing it for the first time).
- 2) Explain typical day-to-day usage of AiiDA for individual members of the THEOS team. This would give a good overview of the capabilities of AiiDA
- 3) Don't use Amazon cloud. Instead, explain users how to install AiiDA for their own "production" clusters.

The tutorial was very well organized. Documentation very well written and easy to follow. Tutors and developers were open to answer to questions and supportive. All in all I would totally recommend a tutorial like this to anyone interested in learning about AiiDA.

Some suggestions for future schools:

* I found the level of python knowledge required higher than basic, as described in the announcement (this is not a negative point in general, it was actually challenging, but I would make it clearer in the description of the tutorial)

* in order to better understand how to deal with the aiiida database I missed a description of the structure of the database (which are the possible types of nodes, how are they connected, how to navigate the database)... This point was discussed during the tutorial several times, but I have the impression that a structured description would have been useful

Very good tutorial.

I have to admit I had some problems following the tasks. Mainly I was a little unsure how deep and when to get into to source code, for really understanding what happens, or when just changing the supplied code appropriately. So the kind of switching between source code documentation and real tasks was kind of difficult.

But I would rather say this is my problem. So I can't say how you could improve things, rather I would say I could have approached the tasks differently.

I guess I can give better feedback, when I really get more into using AiiDA.

Report on the “Python for Scientific Computing” tutorial.

Modena (Italy), 25-27 Jan. 2016

The aim of the tutorial was to introduce researchers and PhD students to the python programming language. The tutorial was attended by 26 students, postdocs and researchers. The participants were then invited to compile an online feedback form (about the 50% of them compiled the form). The results show that the tutorial was highly appreciated by the participants.

The first series of plots concern the evaluation of the topic of the course. As pointed out by the feedback collected, the majority of participants consider python a power tool for computational scientists and useful for their daily work.

The second series of plots concern the course contents. The results reported below indicate that the participants found the arguments of the course clearly explained and the course contents “satisfying”.

The third series of plots concern the self-assessed level of knowledge of python of the participants, before and after the tutorial. Noticeably, at the start of the tutorial, the relative

majority of the participants declared a poor level of knowledge of python: this condition is no-longer present at the end of the course when the major of the participants declared a “satisfactory” level of skill/knowledge of python.

The fourth plot points out the final evaluation of the training course. The majority of the participants consider the course “very good” or “excellent”. On a scale 0-5, we can extrapolate from the plot an average rating of 4.2/5.

The results obtained encourage the organization of future tutorials on this topic.

SCIENTIFIC REPORT ON THE WORKSHOP: “MARVEL/MAX/PSI-K TUTORIAL ON HIGH-THROUGHPUT COMPUTATIONS: GENERAL METHODS AND APPLICATIONS USING AIIIDA”

JANUARY 19, 2017 GIOVANNI PIZZI
EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland, 22-24 June 2016

Group picture from the AiiDA tutorial, EPFL June 2016

High-throughput computing (HTC) is emerging as an effective methodology in computational materials science for the discovery of novel materials. Its adoption is spreading rapidly at the point that HTC is becoming an essential tool for computational materials scientists.

The aim of the tutorial was to introduce young researchers to HTC, with hands-on tutorials based on the open-source high-throughput platform AiiDA (<http://www.aiida.net>), complemented by three invited highlight talks to underscore the diverse application fields of HTC.

Report

The tutorial was targeted at about 40 students, postdocs and researchers interested in applying high-throughput computations in their research, and in particular to those interested in learning how to use the AiiDA platform.

It started in the morning of Wednesday 22 June. After the registration formalities and a short introduction by the workshop organizers, Giovanni Pizzi (EPFL) gave a first introduction talk on AiiDA and the design concepts behind it, essential to understand the code but more generally to efficiently manage high-throughput computations: the ADES model, the concepts of provenance and reproducibility, and how these can be achieved using AiiDA.

Hands-on sessions

After the coffee break, we started the first of a series of hands-on sessions with AiiDA. The room was large enough to host all participants, each of them working on a different computer (either their laptop, or on machines provided by EPFL). Each session was always introduced by the instructors, who briefly explained the aim of the session. The detailed instructions on the tasks to achieve were then provided on a printed booklet (and also on a PDF file), so that participants could learn at their own pace. Eight instructors (see list below) were available throughout all sessions to answer to specific questions any participant could have had.

Sessions were interleaved with invited talks (see below) and with coffee breaks.

Participants were extremely interested in learning the code – actually, instructors were quite surprised to see that most participants were so eager to learn that they would not leave the room during coffee breaks, and had to be “pushed out” out of the room!!

Participants of the tutorial at work

Invited highlight talks

The workshop, however, was also focused more generally on teaching general techniques to be used in high-throughput computations, independent of the code used. For this reason, we have invited three experts in the domain of high-throughput computations.

The first talk, on Wednesday afternoon, was given by Kristian S. Thygesen (DTU, Denmark), with title “Computational screening for new solar energy materials”. The second talk by Gábor Csányi (University of Cambridge, UK) was on Thursday morning and it was titled “Fitting interatomic potentials to moderate and large amounts of DFT data”. Finally, Geoffroy Hautier (Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium) gave a talk on Friday morning on “Accelerating materials discovery through high-throughput computing and data mining”.

All speakers discussed extremely interesting results from their research, showing in particular how they performed computational searches of materials inside known classes, how filtering of results could be performed to reduce the number of candidates and perform very expensive calculations only on a subset of them, and explaining methods that can be applied to extract information from simulations using machine-learning techniques.

Geoffroy Hautier giving a highlight talk at the AiiDA tutorial

Fostering interactions between participants

In order to encourage discussions and exchange between participants, a poster session was organised in the evening of the first day (22nd June), together with a standing dinner.

Seventeen posters were presented, and the participants seemed very interested in discussing in detail each other's work.

Poster session with standing dinner on the evening of the first day

Moreover, each morning started with a half-an-hour discussion session, where each participant was encouraged to ask questions either on technical questions on the AiiDA code, but more generally on their high-throughput research. It was interesting to see how the participants were discussing among them on different ways to solve common problems to tackle when running large numbers of simulations.

Finally, a social dinner took place on Thursday evening at the restaurant “Le Debarcadère” in Saint Sulpice. We were lucky enough to have a very nice and pleasant weather, that allowed us to have dinner on the terrace on the lakeside, facing the Alps, with a beautiful natural landscape.

Finally, it's worth mentioning that, thanks to the generous support of funding entities (Psi-K, MARVEL and **MaX**), it has been possible to provide financial support for the accommodation in a hotel on campus to 23 participants (additionally to covering the organization expenses, and all coffee breaks, the standing dinner during the poster session, and the social dinner on Thursday evening).

This has made it possible to some participants to take part to the tutorial.

Tutorial details

The tutorial that the instructors prepared in the weeks preceding the event was organised to allow for a smooth learning curve, and to get participants interested to learn more, rather than bored by technical details.

For this reason, from the very first session, users were starting to use the code directly, without any initial session on how to install the code. To achieve this, the tutorial was running on Amazon AWS machines, that provided a very consistent and homogeneous environment to all participants, giving at the same time to each of them a different machine to test, learn and practice.

After the end of the tutorial the virtual machines have also been distributed as a downloadable VirtualBox appliance (on <http://www.aida.net/tutorials>). In this way, it becomes extremely easy for participants to run again the tutorial in the future (e.g., optional parts). Most importantly, also for people who could not attend the tutorial can profit of the learning material, and start learning the code with almost zero time required for initial setup (it's just needed to install VirtualBox, download the appliance and start it).

Finally, both the instructor sessions and the invited speaker talks have been recorded and will be available soon online.

Tutorial content

The first sessions focused both on understanding the basic commands to interact with the code, but at the same time participants were getting acquainted with the concept of directed graphs (the way AiiDA internally stores calculations, data and their relationships).

Later, they started to learn how to submit calculations (using Quantum ESPRESSO) with AiiDA. Since in real life errors always occur, we decided to avoid to present a “perfect” tutorial that always works. Instead, the instructions were explicitly asking the user to submit a ‘wrong’ calculation that (for various reasons) would crash, to then teach them how to understand where things went wrong, and how to fix potential problems.

The second day was focused on more advanced topics. First, on how to efficiently query calculations in the database. A test database comprising about 300 calculations on a family of perovskites was already provided, and participants could perform various queries to understand the data, with the final aim of producing a plot to understand which perovskites were metallic, and which were magnetic.

The second very important topic was “workflows”. We first started by introducing the concept of provenance, why it is important to keep track of what has happened, and how to run simulations without “breaking” it. Examples were shown from very simple use cases (like an equation of state). Participants learned how, with a single line, one can ask AiiDA to store the representation of a python function in the database for later querying (using ‘workfunctions’) and how to write full-fledged workflows to automatically obtain a result of interest that originates from a long sequence of calculations.

The session on workflows extended into the morning of the final (third) day, that ended with an explanation of how to install AiiDA and extend it with plugins.

We also had a presentation by Nicolas Mounet, that showed a real-case study from his research: using AiiDA, he could screen over 200,000 materials from 3D databases (ICSD and COD) to filter out only those that are layered (~6000). Those were further refined with extensive DFT calculations to calculate the binding energy and produce a very interesting database of

those (~1800) that are indeed weakly (Van der Waals) bonded and are potentially realisable in the lab using exfoliation techniques.

Results of the feedback form

The feedback received from the participants has been extremely positive. We have been therefore strongly encouraged by them to organize a new event in May 2017, whose registrations are (to date) open: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/en/events/aيدا-tutorial-may-2017>. We report below the main results of the feedback form.

The next two plots compare the self-assessed level of knowledge of AiiDA of the participants before and after the tutorial. Remarkably, participants with a “poor” level of knowledge, which represented the relative majority before the tutorial, were no longer present after the tutorial. The vast majority of the self-evaluations after the tutorial was “satisfactory” or better.

Change in the level of skills before and after the tutorial

The following series of plots reports on the evaluations that the instructors received from the participants. The distribution of the responses suggests that the instructors were prepared, available, and capable to effectively motivate the participants.

Results of the feedback form on the instructors

Finally, 81.5% of the participants declared that they would strongly recommend their colleagues to participate to a similar tutorial on high-throughput computations using AiiDA.

Additional information

Workshop organizers

Giovanni Pizzi – EPFL, Switzerland
Andrea Ferretti – CNR, Istituto Nanoscienze, Italy
Boris Kozinsky – Robert Bosch RTC, Cambridge MA, USA

Tutorial instructors

Andrea Cepellotti – EPFL, Switzerland
Fernando Gargiulo – EPFL, Switzerland
Giovanni Pizzi – EPFL, Switzerland
Leonid Kahle – EPFL, Switzerland
Martin Uhrin – EPFL, Switzerland
Nicolas Mounet – EPFL, Switzerland
Snehal Waychal – EPFL, Switzerland
Spyros Zoupanos – EPFL, Switzerland

Invited highlight talks

Gábor Csányi (University of Cambridge, UK): “Fitting interatomic potentials to moderate and large amounts of DFT data”
Geoffroy Hautier (Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium): “Accelerating materials discovery through high-throughput computing and data mining”
Kristian S. Thygesen (DTU, Denmark): “Computational screening for new solar energy materials”
Program

The program is available online at: <http://nccr-marvel.ch/en/events/aiida-tutorial-june-2016>

List of participants

17 among the participants also presented a poster during the evening of the first day.

Michael Atambo, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy
Gabriel Autes, EPFL
Luigi Bagolini, CNR-IOM, Italy
Juan Beltrán, IMDEA Materials, Spain
Lilia Boeri, TU Graz, Austria
Marco Borelli, SISSA, Italy
Ariadni Boziki, EPFL
Jens Bröder, Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH, Germany
Claudia Cardoso, CNR–Istituto Nanoscienze, Italy
Andrea Cepellotti, EPFL
Francesca Costanzo, ICN2, Spain
Gábor Csányi, University of Cambridge, UK
Pietro Delugas, SISSA, Italy
Bonny Dongre, Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany

Mahdi Faghihnasiri, Shahrood University of Technology, Iran
Matteo Fasano, Politecnico di Torino, Italy
Andrea Ferretti, CNR–Istituto Nanoscienze, Italy
Fernando Gargiulo, EPFL
Jacek Golebiowski, Imperial College London, UK
Ionel Bogdan Guster, ICN2, Spain
Geoffroy Hautier, Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium
Vinay Hedge, Northwestern University, USA
Sergio Illera, ICN2, Spain
Farzaneh Jahanbakhshi, EPFL
Conrad Johnston, Queen’s University Belfast, UK
Leonid Kahle, EPFL
Vamshi Mohan, Katukuri EPFL
Ryo Kobayashi Shiga, EPFL and Nagoya Institute of Technology, Japan
Boris Kozinsky, Bosch RTC, Cambridge, USA
Chan-Woo Lee, Korea Institute of Energy Research, South Korea
Ariel Lozano, Basque Center for Applied Mathematics, Spain
Changru Ma, EPFL
Ivan Marri, CNR–Istituto Nanoscienze, Italy
Henrique Miranda, Université du Luxembourg, Luxembourg
Hossein Mirhosseini, MPI Dresden, Germany
Stephan Mohr, Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain
Matthieu Mottet, IBM Research Zurich and EPFL
Nicolas Mounet, EPFL
Silviya Ninova, University of Bern
Diego Pasquier, EPFL
Xu Pengxiang, ETH Zürich
Riccardo Petraglia, EPFL
Simone Piccinin, CNR-IOM, Italy
Giovanni Pizzi, EPFL
Miguel Pruneda, ICN2, Spain
Clelia Righi, CNR–Istituto Nanoscienze, Italy
Iliia Sivkov, ETH Zürich
Olga Syzgantseva, Aalto University, Finland
Kristian S. Thygesen, DTU, Denmark
Iurii Timrov, EPFL
Martin Uhrin, EPFL
Joel Voiselle, EPFL
Snehal Waychal, EPFL
Brandon Wood, Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, USA
Aliaksandr Yakutovich, Empa
Felipe Zapata, Ruiz VU Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

5 Dec - 7 Dec 2016 – Cineca Bologna

1. Information about the school was... ?

2. Registration was... ?

3. The venue was... ?

4. Catering was... ?

5. The overall organization was... ?

Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

5 Dec - 7 Dec 2016 – Cineca Bologna

6. The topics were relevant for my work/research interests ?

7. I was inspired to new ways of thinking ?

8. The lectures were clearly presented and comprehensible ?

9. The pace of teaching was right ?

10. Teaching aids used (e.g. slides) were well prepared ?

Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

5 Dec - 7 Dec 2016 – Cineca Bologna

11. Hands-on exercises and demonstrations were a valuable contribution to the school?

12. Social event(s) were an enjoyable and important aspect of the school?

13. What did you like most about the course?

- QMMM approach
- The quality of some of the presentations, in particular the one of Anton, the one of SIESTA and the one of Yambo
- The opportunity of getting infos about new codes and numerical techniques.
- The possibility to learn the new codes as well as to prepare it for a specific application.
- Novel future perspective (exascale). Different codes employed. Contacts with people working in similar research field.

14. What did you like least about the course?

- previous information was not enough detailed to understand properly the level or focus of the course.
- Nothing
- -
- Not all the slides were available at the course time

15. Additional comments on the content, specific lectures, etc.

- too much codes were presented, so the details on each were not too clear. I think it is better to focus on less arguments and doing more hands on
- None
- Aiida usefulness was not really clear. Hands on Siesta tutorials could be more focused on parallel implementation.

* 16. Overall, how would you rate this school?

Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

5 Dec - 7 Dec 2016 – Cineca Bologna

17. In the future, I will need training in general HPC programming (MPI, OpenMP)...

18. In the future, I will need training in advanced HPC programming (Hybrid MPI-OpenMP; next-gen HPC languages e.g. PGAS; GPU computing e.g. CUDA)...

19. In the future, I will need training in code optimisation and performance analysis...

20. In the future, I will need training in porting of existing codes to HPC architectures...

Material Science codes on innovative HPC architectures: targeting exascale

5 Dec - 7 Dec 2016 – Cineca Bologna

don't know || 0%

21. In the future, I will need training in specific HPC application(s)... ?

22. In the future, I will need training in HPC programming and applications specific to my research community... ?

23. In the future, I will need training in visualisation techniques... ?

24. Are there some other fields of training you feel PRACE should provide training events in? ?

- None
- Rules and style of writing an HPC code using modern Fortran and C/C++ Application of MPI at KNC/KNL
- Systems Dynamics

25. Please give any other general comments about PRACE training activities. ?

- None
- An excursion to Marconi could be a very good supplement of the school.
- they could be very important in order to form and enforce strong linked community of users and developpers

Scientific Report on the Workshop:

"Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using Quantum ESPRESSO"

Introduction

The goal of the Workshop was to enable participating scientists to combine the most advanced approaches to quantum materials simulation with an in-depth understanding of modern parallel architectures. The intensive program offered theoretical and technical lectures, as well as demonstrations and dedicated hands-on sessions exploring high-performance computing (HPC) facilities for scientific production.

Participants learned how to handle more efficiently the research codes in the Quantum ESPRESSO distribution along with the Yambo code, and to handle the AiiDA framework to manage, store, share, and disseminate the workload.

The Workshop

The Workshop was held from Jan 16 to 27 at the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) in collaboration with the Quantum ESPRESSO Foundation and the Max EU Centre of Excellence for HPC applications, with the participation of CECAM, the Psi-k electronic-structure network, the MARVEL National Centre of Competence in Research and the eCam EU Centre of Excellence for HPC applications. The two-weeks event have seen the participation of 65 selected attendees (selected from over 270 received applications), 6 directors, 2 local organizers, 16 invited lecturers and 6 invited instructors to support of the lab-session for an overall participation from 30 different countries worldwide.

The number of selected participants was limited mainly by the capacity of the computer laboratory in order to guarantee a fruitful experience during the lab-sessions to all participants. Thanks to the generous support of funding entities (Psi-k, MARVEL, MaX, CECAM and e-CAM), it has been possible to provide financial support for the accommodation in the ICTP guest houses on campus to 24 participants. At the same

time, the ICTP provided independently also financial support for flight and accommodation to about 25 participants from developing countries. Thanks to these generous sponsorships, the organizers also provided meal coupons for the ICTP cafeteria, coffee-breaks and a reception dinner.

Many of the selected participants would not have been able to attend this workshop without receiving such a financial contribution to cover their costs of participation.

The venue

Historically, the ICTP represents a unique location for scientific meetings, providing a number of in-place services such as housing, bank, operation and administration while including high-standard facilities for lectures and lab-sessions. It offers the possibility to provide lodging to large number of participants within the same building where both lectures and hands-on are delivered. The entire workshop administration was handled by the ICTP. The picture below shows the feedback obtained from participants for the evaluation of the venue. There as an almost unanimous positive judgement of the venue as well as of the overall organization.

The ICTP also provided the opportunity to record all lectures using the MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) tool, named slideshot [1], developed at EPFL, Lausanne. Video lectures will be made available soon within the MaX portal [2], a youtube channel as well as the slideshot video library [3].

The Program

The entire program reported in the official workshop webpage [4] was designed for having direct lectures in the morning and afternoon hands-on sessions. During the first week participants have been exposed to a large number of topics from foundations of DFT to *ab-initio* molecular dynamics and from linear response to spectroscopy. While in the second week the focus was on advanced topics such as the exploitation of parallel systems for HPC, including high-throughput. In particular, three days were dedicated to the AiiDA tutorial and to understand the hierarchy of parallelism in the Quantum ESPRESSO distribution. During the second week, the Yambo code and the i-PI interface were also presented. All the scientific software presented during the workshop are supported and developed within the Max EU Centre of Excellence for HPC applications.

Lectures

The lectures in the mornings covered a wide variety of topics, starting from the fundamentals of density-functional theory (DFT) and its implementation using plane-waves and pseudopotentials to more advanced topics. Those included electronic structure calculations beyond standard DFT, advanced functionals, molecular dynamics, linear response (phonons and spectroscopy), optical properties and solvent effects. Some lectures also covered the use of AiiDA for complex workflows and views on the

future development of HPC.

Hands-on sessions

All hands-on sessions were hosted at the main info-lab available at the ICTP, which includes approximately 50 Linux stations. However, due to the larger number of participants, some were following from their own laptop.

To guarantee a homogeneous working environment for all participants, a Docker image containing most of the tutorial was prepared. After the workshop, all participants were also provided with a USB key containing this Docker image which allows them to continue working in the workshop-environment also at home. Cloud computer resources were offered by CINECA to easily run the Docker image using laptops. Parallel infrastructure for HPC were offered by SISSA on their Ulysses Tier-1 Linux Cluster where a trial account for all participants was created and approximately 30 dedicated computer nodes (equipped with 20-cores each) were made available for the training. Participants were constantly encouraged by the lecturers to use the Ulisse Linux Cluster for running the tutorial, including computational intensive input examples.

Picture of a lab-session taken during the Workshop

Final Evaluation and Conclusion

While this workshop benefited from previous experiences made during schools and workshops on Quantum ESPRESSO, Yambo and AiiDA, it contained a significant amount of new teaching material. In order to evaluate the new workshop concept and material, an online questionnaire was provided to the participants in the end of the workshop.

About 70% of the participants took part in the evaluation. The received feedback is extremely positive and reflects the overall enthusiasm registered among the attendees during the two-weeks event.

The first interesting aspect is to analyse the participants' own judgement of how this workshop has impacted on their skills in HPC. The results, depicted below, show an evident shift towards excellence, which underlines that the participants consider to have obtained a significant benefit from attending this workshop. Moreover, more than 90% of participants ranked above 7 (in a range from 0 to 10) their willingness to further recommend this kind of workshop to colleagues.

Workshop impact on skills

In regards to the course contents more than 90% of the participants have declared to either agree or strongly agree about:

- the learning objectives were clear;
- the course content was satisfying, organized and well planned;
- the learned topics were matching the expectations;
- talks from invited lecturers were useful and fitting the expected topics.

The following figures report instead the evaluations related to the lecturers and also the contribution of the invited instructors for support of the lab-sessions.

Quality of the Lectures

Skill and responsiveness of the Instructors

Taking into consideration that the concept of the workshop was new and significantly different from previous activities organized by the workshop directors and staff, such positive feedback from the participants is extremely encouraging. All lecture material - lab-sessions tutorials, video lectures and the Dockers images containing a self-contained environment for running the tutorials - is publicly available online to the scientific community. Therefore, the objective of building a set of up-to-date lecture material for further editions of similar events was completely achieved.

In conclusion, this workshop has served to build a prototype event for future

dissemination efforts long similar thematic lines. The very positive feedback from participants with a wide variety of scientific and cultural backgrounds prove that the chosen concept is well suited for the purpose.

Final Evaluation and Conclusion

[1] <http://slideshow.epfl.ch/>

[2] <http://www.max-centre.eu/>

[3] <http://slideshow.epfl.ch/events/17>

[4] <http://indico.ictp.it/event/7921/>

Electronic Structure: from blackboard to source code

Week 1

Lecture 1-2: Introduction to Density Functional Theory. *The basic approximations: Born Oppenheimer adiabatic approximation and the effective potential concept. How does the effective potential look like (example: Hartree Fock)? DFT: Density as the basic quantity, Hohenberg-Kohn theorem and variational principle, Kohn-Sham auxiliary equations. Variational principle and the Hellmann-Feynman and stress theorems. The band structure interpretation and its shortcomings, band gap problem, Janak's theorem.*

Lecture 3: General description of a plane-wave pseudopotential code. *Self-consistent cycle vs global minimization and Car-Parrinello method. Block diagram of a SCF-type and a CP-type code. The basic modules: diagonalization/minimization (needs $H^*\psi$), building the density (needs BZ sampling), building the potential (needs Poisson's solver and exchange-correlation functionals). Initialization (the external potential) and termination (forces/stress and ionic evolution). The KS hamiltonian and wave functions in a PW basis set. Fast Fourier transform and the dual space formalism. How things scale with system dimensions ? Why do we need pseudopotentials ?*

Lecture 4-5: Pseudopotentials. *Empirical pseudopotentials. Transferability. First principles pseudopotential (unscreening of the reference atomic configuration). Norm Conserving Pseudopotentials: PP in the semilocal form, PP in the fully non-local Kleinman-Bylander form. Ghost States. Ultra Soft Pseudopotentials. Generalized eigenvalue problem and orthogonality. Projection Augmented Wave datasets. Total energy break up in grid and atomic contributions.*

Week 2

Lecture 6: Parallelization. *Parallelization tools and strategies: MPI and OpenMP; data and workload distribution; bandwidth and latency. Basic parallel operations (checkpoint, broadcast, collect, gather/scatter); communication intensive operations. Amdahl's law. Strong and weak scalability. Hierarchy of parallelization levels. Porting computational intensive modules to GPUs.*

Lecture 7: Solving the KS equation. *Iterative diagonalization drivers: Davidson diagonalization; Conjugate Gradient; DIIS. Hamiltonian preconditioning. Efficient evaluation of the KS hamiltonian and overlap matrix by dual space formalism and Kleinman-Bylander pseudopotential decomposition.*

Lecture 8: Symmetry. *How to use crystal symmetry to reduce the computational work load. Symmetrization of density, energy, forces and other tensorial quantities. Special points for BZ integration. Automatic generation of k-point grids. Gamma point special features.*

Lecture 9: Building the new charge density. *Brillouin zone sampling: periodic vs non periodic systems; metallic vs non metallic; magnetic vs non magnetic. US/PAW augmentation charges; real space vs reciprocal space approach. Charge density mixing: simple mixing; Broyden mixing. Error estimate, charge sloshing, preconditioning: Thomas Fermi and local TF mixing.*

Lecture 10: Building the new potential. *Hartree energy and potential and its corrections for isolated systems. Exchange-correlation functionals (no hybrids yet). Energy in LDA and GGA and how to take its derivative with respect to density.*

Week 3

Lecture 11-12: Advanced xc functionals. *Hybrids, implementation and challenges. Fock operator in a plane-wave approach; nested self-consistent loop; adaptively compressed exchange (ACE). Van der Waals functionals; Roman Perez-Soler interpolation scheme.*

Lecture 13: Density Functional Perturbation Theory. *DFPT and lattice dynamical calculations. Block diagram of a linear response code. Consequences of symmetry. Definition and solution of the linear systems. Evaluation of the density response. Perturbed self-consistent potential. Computation of the dynamical matrix.*

Lecture 14-15: Further optional topics. *Spin-orbit and relativistic extensions; electron-phonon interactions; modern theory of macroscopic polarization; Car-Parrinello molecular dynamics.*